

Creativity and (social) security. Using art-based to contain and prevent Online IDentity Theft

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The digitalization of society has provided criminals with new opportunities to obtain and misuse personal identity information. The emergence and spread of Online IDentity Theft (OIDT) is an example of this. As users, we, directly, generate data and assume risks, not always consciously. However, OIDT can potentially affects anyone. Very little is known about the profile, needs, socio-emotional experiences, risks of people whose identity information has been compromised or misused. European victims of OIDT often do not report the crime, believing that the harm suffered is not significant enough or lacking adequate material and immaterial resources to counteract it. With the aim of expanding information, education, and awareness on OIDT, an interdisciplinary team (sociologists and artist) has conducted an experimental project at the University of Bologna developing art-based projects. The narrations, practical information and emotional dynamics have been outlined by 23 semi-structured interviews with OIDT experts and 47 structured interviews with victims. Key informants' perspectives were the starting point to create visuals. As a direct outcome, sociologists and artist realized: (1) a care kit cards (2) a comic strip (3) a "riskymeter" infographic. In this scenario, visual projects which merge social research and art, were designed to 1) educate users, victims, and professionals to prevent Online Identity Theft with socio-pedagogical resources 2) inform on various possibilities to report and be assisted 3) raise awareness about social security and empowerment